

FLAME NEWSLETTER – ISSUE 4

National Observatory of Athens

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FLAME is a research project carried out at the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). The overarching goal of the project is the study and characterization of the environmental conditions that promote extreme wildfires in Greece, intending to increase awareness and enhance the preparedness of fire operatives and the public.

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Editorial

Welcome to **Issue 4** of FLAME's e-Newsletter!

During the period from July to November 2022, our research team continued working on advancing our understanding of extreme fire weather and extreme fire behavior in Greece and Europe. To increase public awareness, we released FLAME's second promotional video, talking about extreme wildfires and the environmental conditions that promote their occurrence. Further, we published the first handbook on synoptic-scale pyrometeorology, presenting the critical fire weather patterns of Greece and discussing how they relate to different levels of fire danger. We also launched a new analysis focusing on changing fire weather extremes across Europe, and results will be soon available through a scientific publication.

FLAME's fourth newsletter is dedicated to two brief reviews of the 2022 fire season in Europe and Greece. We also present dissemination actions that took place over the reporting period (July to November), both inside and outside the scientific community.

Enjoy reading!

Theodore M. Giannaros
Principal Investigator of FLAME
IERSD/NOA
14.12.2022

REVIEW OF THE 2022 FIRE SEASON IN EUROPE

The **2022 fire season** in Europe was **unprecedented** in terms of burned areas and periods of extremely anomalous fire weather conditions over large areas of western and central Europe. Extreme fire weather conditions were driven by several prolonged heatwave episodes and long-term drought. During the summer of 2022, several European countries witnessed record-breaking temperatures and burned areas. According to the official records of the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS - <https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu>), the cumulative burned area in Europe equaled **749,113 ha** as of September 3, 2022 (see image below).

An examination of climatic data derived from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) reveals that **the summer of 2022 in Europe was the warmest on record**. The average annual (summer) temperature of 2022 was **+2.75 °C** higher than the 1991 – 2020 long-term average (see image below), setting a new record by a substantial margin of +0.4 °C, compared to the previous warmest year on record (2021).

ERA5 JJA mean FWI anomalies

The compound effect of extremely anomalous temperatures and long-term drought was the prevalence of **anomalous fire weather** over major areas of western and central Europe. Analysis of the Fire Weather Index (FWI) of the Canadian Forest Fire Weather Index System (CFFWIS) data provided by the European Centre for Medium-range

Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) reveals large positive anomalies (i.e., adverse fire weather, conducive to the rapid spread of wildfires) over most of western and central Europe (see image on the left). The largest positive anomalies appear to coincide with the areas most affected by wildfires during the summer of 2022, i.e., Spain, France, southeast England, Germany, and central Italy. Overall, the 2022 fire season in Europe was characterized by **record-breaking extreme fire weather conditions**, driven primarily by extreme and prolonged periods of **anomalously high temperatures and long-term drought**.

REVIEW OF THE 2022 FIRE SEASON IN GREECE

The 2022 fire season in Greece was characterized by **below-average burned areas** and **near-normal fire weather conditions**. According to the data provided by the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS - <https://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu>), the total area burned in Greece from January 1, 2022, to October 31, 2022, is estimated at ~20,000 ha (see image below), corresponding to about 50 % of the average annual burned area for the period 2006 – 2021.

Total accumulated burnt area (ha) during May - October 2022

ERA5 May–October mean FWI anomalies

Analysis of data provided by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) reveals that the western and northern parts of the country experienced above-average temperatures throughout most of the fire season period (i.e., from June to October 2022). In terms of fire weather conditions, examination of the Fire Weather Index (FWI) component of the Canadian Forest Fire Weather Index System (CFFWIS) reveals **near- or below-average conditions** for most parts of Greece, except the northeastern continental parts and eastern Aegean islands,

where above-average fire weather conditions can be seen (see image on the left).

A temporal analysis of the country-mean FWI during the period May – October (see image below) reveals near- or below-average fire weather conditions for most of the time. A period of above-average fire weather conditions prevailed from July 15 to August 10. This period was accompanied by increased fire activity and the most destructive fires in the eastern and southern parts of the country. The fire weather conditions during this period were associated with the combination of hot, dry, and mostly windy conditions across the eastern and southern parts of the country. These fire weather conditions were primarily driven by the establishment of a persistent blocking pattern (upper-tropospheric high-pressure system) over western and central

Europe that extended to the Balkans. The establishment of this atmospheric blocking was accompanied by enhanced north/northeasterly winds (Etesian winds) over the Aegean Sea and the eastern and southern continental parts of the country.

FLAME PUBLICITY FACTS

Publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals

-

Conference posters and presentations

Giannaros TM, Bezes A, Dafis S, Dragozi E, Karagiannidis A, Koletsis I, Kotroni V, Kyros G, Lagouvardos K, Papavasileiou G (2022) Firescope: A fire weather information and early warning system supporting the shift from suppression to prevention in Europe and Greece. Safe Greece 2022, Thessaloniki, Greece, 29 September – 01 October 2022. Proceedings are available online [here](#).

Papavasileiou G, Giannaros TM (2022) Critical fire weather patterns of Greece: Forecasting fire weather conditions in the medium-range. Safe Greece 2022, Thessaloniki, 29 September – 01 October 2022. Proceedings are available online [here](#).

Giannaros TM, Papavasileiou G (2022) Spatiotemporal analysis of fire danger extremes in Europe between 1980 and 2019: Preliminary results. IX International Conference on Forest Fire Research, Coimbra, Portugal, 14 – 18 November 2022.

Papavasileiou G, Giannaros TM (2022) Validation of ERA5 fire weather conditions in Greece between 2007 and 2019: A preliminary analysis. IX International Conference on Forest Fire Research, Coimbra, Portugal, 14 – 18 November 2022.

FLAME in the media

<https://www.mynews.gr/giannaros-pyrkagies-pyrometeorologia/>

<https://www.kathimerini.gr/society/561965494/fotia-stin-penteli-to-ekriktiko-kokteil-toy-hot-dry-windy-pyrometeorologoi-exigoyn-stin-k/>

<https://www.kathimerini.gr/society/561983947/giati-einai-pio-katastrofikes-oi-pyrkagies-kai-stin-ellada-ta-teleytaia-chronia/>

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